

TRIBAL EDUCATION IN WEST BENGAL WITH SPECIAL REFERENCES TO EKALAVYA MODEL RESIDENTIAL SCHOOLS: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

India has the largest tribal population in the world, accounting for 8.6% of the total population. According to the 2011 Census of India, this accounts for 8.6 percent of the total population of the country. Various initiatives and schemes of the central government and various state governments in India cover the aspect of education for the scheduled tribes. Eklavya Model Residential School (EMRS) is a Government of India scheme for a model residential English medium school, specifically for Scheduled Tribes across India. EMRSs started in 1997–98 to impart quality education to ST children. The schools focus not only on academic education but also on the all-round development of the students. Each school has a capacity of 480 students, from Class VI to XII. The study objective is to assess the functionality of the Eklavya model residential schools situated in West Bengal, taking into consideration different aspects of a school-system and any other important aspect presented. This study will help to know the present condition of the Eklavya Model Residential School Program and help to look beyond the ambiguities concerning the status of these schools. The methodology followed was qualitative in nature. The study has different sources, like data that was gathered through interviews (both with teachers and students), observation by the researcher, and official documents from the Government of India's Ministry of Tribal Affairs. This study can serve as first-hand data on all the Eklavya Model Residential Schools in West Bengal and their current status.

Keywords: Tribal Education, EMRS, Scheduled Tribes, Different Aspects.

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most vital prerequisite for the overall development of a nation, with special importance given to the development of its human resource. But the target is still far from being reached if the right to education is not given to all sections of society. It is particularly necessary to give chances of education to socially and economically backward classes so that they are given educational chances equal to their social and economic status. In the Indian context, priority must be given to the education of backward classes. Since the Scheduled Tribe children are in a disadvantageous position, they must be given the priority. Despite various initiatives and schemes having been initiated by the central as well as state governments for education among the Scheduled Tribes, the implementation is inadequate. The weak implementation of such initiatives is visible in the bad educational condition of the Scheduled Tribe children year after year, as reported in various government and non-government reports.

Scheduled Tribes in India are the most economically as well as socially deprived communities in India. A population of around 10.45 crores makes own tribal population as the largest in the world. This makes them 8.6% of the country's total population, which includes 5.25 crore males and 5.20 crore females. This population was recorded for the decadal growth of 24% from 2001 in the next census, which will take place in 2011.

When any government goes for a plan to improve educational provisions for citizens, those plans mostly address distance from the facilities provided and the population size they are catering to. But these do not usually match the needs of tribal areas. Hence the national and provincial governments of India have realized the need of policies, norms and approaches which are flexible while addressing education of tribal people. So, there is an evident need to apply innovative strategies like community schools or special schools. In response, the government of India took the initiative of establishing Eklavya Model Residential Schools (EMRS) at localities where the scheduled tribe population is incidentally higher.

EMRS is a Government of India scheme for a model residential English medium school, specifically for Scheduled Tribes across India. EMRSs started in 1997-98 to impart quality education to ST children. The schools focus not only on academic education but also on the all-round development of the students. Each school has a capacity of 480 students, from Class VI to XII. The EMRSs in West Bengal (Total 7) were established in two phases. In the districts of (Jalpaiguri, Burdwan, Purulia, Bankura and Jhargram) the EMRSs are functioning since the academic year 1997-98 and the rest two EMRSs of Dakshin Dinajpur and Birbhum district are functioning since the academic session 2005-06. In the midst of the conflict between a very noble initiative by the government which is reportedly running successfully and the reports and research outcomes on the same which reflects a different story it is essential to point out the actual case and dig deeper.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out if the objectives stated by Ministry of Tribal Affairs for Eklavya model residential school program are being fulfilled by the schools under this program.
- To assess the functionality of the Eklavya model residential schools taking in consideration different aspects of a school-system, namely;- Teaching-Learning-Evaluation, Infrastructural Facilities, Human Resources, Student Progression, Co-curricular Activities and any other important aspect presented.
- To explore the prevalent problems these schools are facing at present and the probable solutions for the problems at hand.
- To know how much the educational provision provided by these schools help their students in attaining achievement in higher education or placement in future life.
- To study how much these schools help their students to be acquainted with their tribal culture.

METHODOLOGY

Case study method was adopted by the researcher for this particular study. The study was qualitative in nature. It was an intrinsic organizational case study.

Target Institutions

Sl No	Name of the Institution	Location	District
1	Eklavya Model Residential H.S. School	Nagrakata	Jalpaiguri
2	Eklavya Model Residential School	Kuarsal, Buniadpur	Dakshin Dinajpur
3	Eklavya Model Residential High School	Kankutia, Bolpur	Birbhum
4	Eklavya Model Residential School	Raghunathpur	Burdwan
5	Eklavya Model Residential School	Susunia, Manbazar-II	Purulia
6	Eklavya Model Residential School	Mukutmonipur, Gorabari	Bankura
7	Ramakrishna Mission Vidyamandira (EMRS)	Satyaban Palli, Jhargram	Jhargram

Participants

Tools

- Observation as a Tool
- Information Bank for HOI
- Open-ended Questionnaire for the Teachers
- Open-ended Questionnaire for the Students
- Interview Schedule for the Resource Person

Techniques of Data Analysis

Collected data in the form of data bank with the help of observation was analyzed by comparing data obtained from different institutions and presented in tabular forms.

All other data collected in written form using open-ended questionnaire or interview-schedule was analyzed by qualitative content analysis through the following steps;

Then corroborated using data collected from the resource person.

Comparative representation of data gathered using information blank is done. The data gathered in written form (data collected from participants) are analyzed by qualitative content analysis through generation of relevant codes and themes. Data collected from resource person through interview is presented and used for corroboration of previously collected data.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁: *Do the schools aim at overall development of the students as stated in the objectives for the Eklavya Model Residential School program by the Ministry of Tribal Affairs?*

- The teachers of EMRSs of West Bengal are found to be very much concerned about the overall development of the students. Not only cognitive development through teaching-learning, but also physical and social aspects of developments are taken care of by regular physical activities, ensuring timely intake of food, involvement in various cultural programs, different exposure programs, inter-school tournaments and making them confident to express their own thoughts.
- The Tribal Development Department of West Bengal government takes various initiatives regularly to improve the condition of EMRSs from the inception of this school programme in this state keeping in mind all-round development of the students belonging to Scheduled Tribes.

- One of the objectives of EMRS programme is to provide children belonging to Scheduled Tribes with quality education. In West Bengal the district of Maldah has one of the higher ST populations. Yet, there is no EMRS established till date.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₂: *Do the schools provide educational support to students according to their different levels?*

- According to the objectives of EMRS scheme, these schools are to provide educational support to the students of VI to X standard separately from the students of XI-XII standard. Among the seven EMRSs present in West Bengal, Birbhum and Dakshin Dinajpur till now don't have any Higher-Secondary standard students. Apart from these two, all other EMRSs have facilities for providing Higher-Secondary students with special coaching. Special exposures are given to H.S. students of Paschim Medinipur by making them participate in camps, institution visits, providing them with information about job and career, making them seat in competitive examinations. In Purulia too, the H.S. level students are provided with career and job-oriented information. The Higher Secondary level students need a proper laboratory set up, which is absent in most of the EMRSs of West Bengal.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₃: *Does the fund provided is being properly used or sufficient for providing remuneration to the staff and upkeep of the educational facilities?*

- According to the teaching and non-teaching staff of the all seven EMRSs of West Bengal the salary provided to them is not sufficient and it is much lower than same category staff of other government or government-aided schools. The dissatisfaction concerning salary is supported by the resource person too. The overall condition of educational facilities from the school building itself to the teaching-learning materials is not very good in these schools, except Birbhum and Paschim Medinipur.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₄: *Does the infrastructural facilities satisfy educational, physical, environmental and cultural needs of students?*

- Infrastructural facilities such as school building, learning materials, hostel building etc in the EMRSs of West Bengal need much more improvement if it is to satisfy the educational needs of students. The laboratories are in a sorry state in most of these institutions. No proper library facility provided in some of them. The teachers and students of all these institutions expressed the need of integrating ICT into the classrooms.
- The physical and environmental condition of all these institutions is basically good. But in some of them there exists lack of proper maintenance and needs immediate renovation and regular cleaning. All these schools are situated in locations far from crowded cities. All of these institutions have huge compounds. The EMRSs of Burdwan, Bankura, Purulia, Jalpaiguri, Dakshin Dinajpur need more maintenance of the school compounds outside school building by decorative gardening or more plantations of trees, clearing of the bushes etc. The school and hostel buildings of Burdwan, Bankura and Purulia are also in a very sorry state.

- All the EMRSs of West Bengal take initiatives to make the students culturally aware. In all these institutions students take part in cultural programmes organized by themselves with the help of teachers on occasions like observation of days with national or cultural importance, annual function, Saraswati Puja etc.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₅: *Do the schools under Eklavya model residential school program function properly in the aspects of teaching, learning and evaluation?*

- Admission process in all the EMRSs involves taking admission test. Age-appropriate admission policy is not found in practice in most of these institutions.
- Although the schools under EMRS scheme are built as English-medium schools, in West Bengal, English is not used as the only medium of teaching in EMRSs.
- In most of the schools TLMs are not available as required. Even in schools which have a good number TLM, those are not used regularly by teachers. In EMRSs of Burdwan, Bankura, Dakshin Dinajpur TLMs are not used at all.
- Use of computers is a part of modern education system. There are computer laboratory present in each of the EMRSs. But in some of the institutions the computer laboratories are not maintained or upgraded making them unusable.
- All the schools are found to maintain provisional routine on daily basis.
- Less importance is given to class-test or remedial examination in most of these schools. The resource person interviewed informed the same. But, in all of them special classes are taken for weaker students. These data is supported by the resource person's feedback. Also, the teachers try to inform guardians about progress or problems of their wards either in parent-teacher meetings or by meeting the guardians personally.
- In all the EMRSs the summative evaluation is purely internal. No questions are borrowed or examiners are hired in any of these institutions.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₆: *Do the schools under Eklavya Model Residential School program are involved in any innovative or best practices concerning teaching, learning or evaluation?*

- Very few innovative approaches are found concerning teaching-learning-evaluation in EMRSs of West Bengal. In some of them there are special classes or courses provided to students of Jalpaiguri, computer-assisted foreign language learning facility in Burdwan, special exposure programmes for students of Paschim Medinipur etc. But overall innovation is less. Most of the teachers of these schools follow the chalk and talk method only.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₇: *Do the schools under EMRS program function properly in the aspects of providing proper infrastructural facilities?*

- In all of EMRSs the infrastructural facilities of the school building are found to be good. There are some problems considering maintenance of those existing facilities as observed and reported by the resource person. Specifically in Bankura and Burdwan the building was well-structured learning but now in bad condition due to zero maintenance. There are issues with proper level of cleanliness in Purulia too. In South Dinajpur and Bankura there is a shortage of water supply in school building.
- The infrastructural conditions of class rooms in Jalpaiguri, Dakshin Dinajpur, Birbhum, Bankura and Paschim Medinipur are observably good. There are issues with maintenance of classroom furniture in Purulia and Burdwan. Cleanliness of the class rooms is not properly maintained in EMRSs of Burdwan, Purulia and Bankura. No multipurpose hall, prayer room and students' common rooms in school building of any of the EMRSs. All the schools have a specific area dedicated for assembly of students before commencement of school. Paschim Medinipur EMRS has a well-structured and well maintained prayer room in hostel premises.
- The library facilities are running properly only in Birbhum and Bankura EMRSs and found to have various types of books in them. In Paschim Medinipur and Purulia various books are present, but students are not found issuing books on regular basis. In Burdwan there is a facility mentioned as library, but actually it is a book bank having only text books. In Dakshin Dinajpur and Jalpaiguri this facility is completely absent.
- No language or Mathematics laboratory present in any of the EMRSs. Overall condition and availability of equipments in laboratories vary between EMRSs of West Bengal. The computer lab of Burdwan is very well equipped but other laboratory set-up is not usable due to absence of power and water supply. In Paschim Medinipur, very well structured Life Science Laboratory set-up with advance equipments present. All the other lab infrastructure and equipments are newly brought, but yet to be set-up. Science laboratory facilities are totally absent in Jalpaiguri and Dakshin Dinajpur. In Purulia and Bankura laboratory instruments are present, but separate space for laboratory of each subject is not available.
- There are some recurring problems in hostel buildings of each EMRS like; one boys' hostel outside main campus in Dakshin Dinajpur, insufficiency of rooms in Burdwan, unhealthy condition of rooms in Purulia, Bankura and Burdwan, problem of water supply in Purulia and Bankura etc. Hostel facilities of Paschim Medinipur and Birbhum are found to be in good condition. According to the resource person, all the schools have proper sanitation facility in school buildings except Purulia. There is water problem in school building of Dakshin Dinajpur and in hostel buildings of Purulia and Bankura. In Purulia and Bankura there are issues with cleanliness of the sanitation facilities in school building. In Paschim Medinipur, the sanitation facility for teachers is excellent. Special facilities available for students in hostels of Birbhum are commendable.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₈: *Do the schools under Eklavya model residential school program function properly in the aspects of human resource management?*

- Human resource shortage is present in most of the EMRSs of West Bengal. Managing the human resource available depends upon efficiency and good relationship of school management or head of the institution with rest of the staff. At present only in Paschim Medinipur this situation is as per expectation. In all other EMRSs of West Bengal there are one or more issues concerning relationship of head of the institution or the management or the government officer in charge with rest of the staff. This particular problem is mirrored in the opinion of the resource person. Although in Dakshin Dinajpur, Birbhum and Paschim Medinipur the teaching and non-teaching staffs are found to be very much enthusiastic and have good relationship among them.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₉: *How do the schools under EMRS program function in the aspects of student progression?*

- There are small initiatives like giving students special coaching during the evening, special coaching for students appearing in board examinations in Bankura and Purulia etc. There are special initiatives too like special lectures by army officials in Jalpaiguri, special exposure programmes and classes by resource persons in Paschim Medinipur, special talks by professionally successful ex-students in Purulia, foreign language learning facility in Burdwan etc. There are very few initiatives observed or noted regarding students' progression beyond curricular and co-curricular activities in Dakshin Dinajpur.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁₀: *How do the schools under Eklavya model residential school program function in the aspects of co-curricular activities?*

- The students are on regular basis involved in various co-curricular activities in all the EMRSs of West Bengal. All the EMRSs have facilities of games and sports for both girls and boys. Although according to the students and the resource person interviewed, the facilities are not upto the mark. Some of the EMRSs organise inter-school tournaments. Students of Burdwan and Birbhum participated in various sports meets up to national level and succeeded. Although in some of the EMRSs sports equipments are not sufficiently present which creates problem for the students. According to the resource person interviewed, initiatives to promote students' potential in matters of sports is less. The students are involved in organizing cultural programmes in various occasions throughout the year. In many EMRSs guest teachers or trainers are hired for giving students song, dance or painting lessons. Students of Paschim Medinipur participated in Republic Day march-past in Kolkata and got special recognition for the same.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁₁: *What are the prevalent problems in running of the schools under EMRS program?*

- There is a problem regarding administration in most of the EMRSs except Paschim Medinipur. In some cases like Dakshin Dinajpur and Jalpaiguri the requirements of

students and teachers are put forward to management but the materials don't reach the school on time.

- There is a major dissatisfaction among all teaching and non-teaching staff regarding salary. Without proper remuneration the staff of these schools may become reluctant.
- There is another problem regarding appointment of teachers. The teachers are appointed on contract basis. They have a constant fear of losing their jobs.
- There is problem with up-gradation of teaching-learning process in most of the cases, as most of the teachers till now follow only lecture method in the class.
- Library is an important part of any educational institution. There is an immediate need of improving the library facilities in all the EMRSs of West Bengal.
- Proper and sufficient residential facilities for teachers are not available in most of the EMRSs of West Bengal.
- Students coming from feeder sections for admission are of very low quality in general. These students come with almost no orientation about English language making it a hard job for teachers to teach them in English.
- The feeder school system funded by the state government is not yielding expected results at present. As an effect of corruption in local authorities, the students coming from the feeder schools don't even get the basic knowledge of English which create a problem when those students get admission in EMRSs.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁₂ : *What can be the probable solutions for the problems present in running of these schools?*

- Job security should be provided to teachers by making their posts permanent.
- Salary increment needed for making the job satisfactory for all staff.
- More communication and exchange of ideas needed between all the EMRSs of West Bengal. It has already started in forms of meetings on regular intervals.
- More importance should be given on development and maintenance of laboratory facilities.
- Supply of materials and making new facilities needed for improvement of teaching-learning should be taken care of immediately.
- Students coming from primary feeder sections should be given basic knowledge of English, so that they can adopt quickly after admission to these schools in sixth standard.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁₃ : *How much does the educational provision provided by these schools help their students in attaining achievement in higher education or placement in future life?*

- Data regarding placement or achievement of students after leaving school is not present in Burdwan and Jalpaiguri. Birbhum and Dakshin Dinajpur are two newly functioning EMRSs and no batch of students has yet faced the higher secondary board exams from these two schools. In Paschim Medinipur and Purulia serious initiatives are taken to provide students with information about competitive examinations and they are given proper career guidance. In Bankura special coaching is given to students who want to appear in state-level joint entrance examination after completion of higher secondary examination.

Findings with respect to Research Question Q₁₄ : *Do the schools under EMRS program help students to be acquainted with their tribal culture?*

- Most of the students enrolled in EMRSs of West Bengal are first generation learners. Their guardians were found to be either farmers or daily labors. But their ward, the present students of EMRS aspire to be teachers, doctors, nurses, police men, army personnel etc. Almost all of them said they want to continue their study beyond school level. This can be said that the schooling of these students in EMRS built their urge to modernize themselves through education and be more sanskritized themselves.
- The students of these schools are made aware of cultures outside their tribal culture through various curricular and co-curricular activities. They are made accustomed to English language. Besides this, in most of the schools under EMRS in West Bengal, the students are supplied with musical instruments of their culture to perform in cultural programmes. In many cases, they are provided with training in tribal dance by professionals. Hool Day is observed in most of the schools and many other occasions are celebrated which have relevance in tribal culture of India. So, it can be said that the students of EMRS are re-tribalized by making them aware of their own rich culture in depth.

CONCLUSION

The magnitude of tribal education is not at all limited in providing the tribal children with formal way of education. It expands beyond the field of formal education. The true aim of tribal education is to make children belonging to Scheduled Tribe communities capable of earning their livelihood, ensuring their over-all development and nurturing their skills.

The EMRS programme conceived by Ministry of Tribal Affairs of Government of India is such a path in which aim of tribal education described in the previous paragraph can be achieved, if the programme is run properly. At state level in West Bengal EMRS programme is run under the supervision of Tribal Development Department, Government of West Bengal. Official documents and information collected from the department indicate that from inception of the EMRS scheme in West Bengal, concerned authorities took numerous initiatives to run the programme systematically in this state. Yet, at the time of study many problems are found to exist concerning the swift running of these schools.

In spite of the existing problems the EMRSs of West Bengal can be considered as having a very good prospect in the field of tribal education. In these institutions ST children not only from this state, but also from neighboring states get the opportunity of good quality education upto Higher Secondary level totally free of cost. There is always room for improvement for any institution, but at present the facilities provided in all the EMRSs are not average or bad. For instance in Birbhum, Paschim Medinipur and Jalpaiguri the school environment is very good. The hostel facilities of two out of seven institutes are very good, three institutions have average hostel facilities and rest two institutions need lots of improvement in the aspect of hostel facilities. The institutions need to improve various aspects of teaching and evaluation. But it can never be said that the teaching and evaluation system at present is awful. Much more exposure and guidance is needed by the students to achieve in future life. Although instances of success of ex-EMRS students in competitive examinations and work-sectors are not very rare.

Hence it can be concluded that although the present condition of EMRSs of West Bengal exhibit many problems in different aspects of school education and administration system, these institutions, upon which the institutional case study is performed, also show the potential to excel in the field of tribal education.

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